

1 **Plasma-induced superhydrophobicity as a green technology for enhanced air-**
2 **gap membrane distillation**

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14 **ABSTRACT**

15 Superhydrophobicity has only recently become a requirement in membrane fabrication and
16 modification. Superhydrophobic membranes have shown improved flux performance and scaling
17 resistance in long-term membrane distillation (MD) operations compared to simply hydrophobic
18 membranes. Here, we introduce plasma micro-nanotexturing followed by plasma deposition as a
19 novel, dry and green method for superhydrophobic membrane fabrication. Using plasma micro-
20 nanotexturing, commercial membranes (WSCA from 40-135 °) are transformed to
21 superhydrophobic (WSCA>150 °, hysteresis <10 °). To this direction, hydrophobic
22 Polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) as well as hydrophilic Cellulose acetate (CA) membranes are
23 transformed to superhydrophobic. The superhydrophobic PTFE membranes showed enhanced
24 water flux in standard air gap membrane distillation and more stable performance compared to
25 the commercial ones for at least 48 h continuous operation, with salt rejection >99.99 %.

26 Additionally, their performance and high salt rejection remained stable, when a low surface
27 tension solution containing SDS/NaCl (55 mN/m) was used, show-casing their anti-wetting
28 properties. The improved performance is attributed to superhydrophobicity and increased pore
29 size after plasma micro-nanotexturing. More importantly, CA membranes, which are initially
30 unsuitable for MD (WSCA \approx 40 °), showed excellent performance with stable flux and salt
31 rejection >99.2 % again for at least 48 hours, demonstrating the effectiveness of the proposed
32 method for wetting control in membranes regardless of their initial wetting properties.

33 **Keywords:** membrane distillation, plasma nanotexturing, superhydrophobic membranes

34

35 **1. Introduction**

36 Membrane Distillation (MD) is a promising method that is being investigated around the world
37 as an alternative, and often as complementary efficient solution for water treatment of
38 challenging feedwaters [1], [2]. During MD, that is a thermally driven separation process, a
39 hydrophobic membrane separates two aqueous solutions at different temperatures by allowing
40 vapor molecules to pass through its pores while preventing mass transfer of liquids. Among the
41 several MD methods, in Air Gap Membrane Distillation (AGMD) vapor exits the membrane on
42 the back side and crosses a gap (hence air-gap) to reach a cold condensing surface [3]. The main
43 advantage of this method is the reduction of heat loss through conduction, thus exhibiting the
44 highest energy efficiency [4]. The feed temperatures typically range from 60 to 90 °C but MD
45 can also work for as low as 40 °C if the temperature difference is sufficient; as a result solar and
46 geothermal energy or waste heat can be incorporated with MD setups.

47 However, there are also many challenges to be addressed before MD becomes a viable clean
48 water production method. First, MD membranes should stop the liquid from entering the pores
49 and should also resist capillary condensation within the pores. Thus, membrane materials are
50 usually limited to hydrophobic polymers, such as Polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) [5]–[7],
51 Polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF) [8]–[13] and PolyPropylene (PP) [14]. Another major drawback
52 in MD is performance deterioration due to scaling. After long time operations the surface of the
53 membrane is covered with salts that clog the pores and reduce the water flux [15]. Thus, recently
54 superhydrophobicity became a common universal goal in membrane fabrication as it has been
55 proven a valuable advantage for improved performance in long term operations (e.g. 100 h) and
56 for high separation efficiency [16],[17].

57 Superhydrophobicity is related with high water static contact angle (WSCA) exceeding 150° and
58 low contact angle hysteresis (CAH) $< 10^\circ$ [18]–[22]. To achieve this, appropriate topography
59 should be combined with a low surface energy material. Although creating a superhydrophobic
60 surface on a bulk material can be trivial, since micro scale roughness is easily obtained, robust
61 and sustainable superhydrophobicity on porous membranes requires more sophisticated methods.
62 In addition, to prevent capillary condensation [23]–[25] superhydrophobicity should also exist
63 inside the three-dimensional shape of the pores.

64 A brief review of the progress in membrane fabrication and modification for MD shows that
65 several researchers attempted the deposition of a rough hydrophobic coating [26]–[32], while
66 others have focused on growing nanofibers or carbon nanotubes on the membrane surface [11],
67 [12], [33]–[41]. However, the criteria of superhydrophobicity have rarely been met. In some
68 recent reports superhydrophobic membranes were fabricated by means of casting polymeric
69 materials and patterning [9], nanofiber formation [11], [42], electrospinning [35], electrospray

70 coating [43], nanofilament growth [44] and nano-imprinting [6]. Some of these
71 superhydrophobic membranes exhibit improved behavior to scaling, even in the presence of
72 other low surface tension surfactants [12], [42]. However, reaching a superhydrophobic state on
73 a membrane may reduce water flux compared to the pristine membranes [12], [14] and usually
74 requires wet, often complex, and non-environmentally friendly methods.

75 Plasma processing, namely etching with simultaneous micro-nano texturing, followed by plasma
76 deposition, on membranes is a dry technology both in vacuum and in atmospheric conditions.
77 Review of the literature shows that it is mainly used for surface functionalization. It is therefore
78 employed either to create hydrophilic groups such as OH, COOH, CO on the surface of the
79 membrane [45]–[47], by exposing it to a flux of free O₂ radicals and ions at low plasma power,
80 or to deposit a hydrophobic polymer on the membrane surface. For example, Yang et al [13],[48]
81 employ plasma deposition processes utilizing fluorocarbon gases resulting in a 30 % increased
82 flux, however they only achieved superhydrophobicity on initially hydrophobic PVDF
83 membranes and the long-term operation of their membranes was not investigated. Notably Gryta
84 et al [49] used a combination of Ar and O₂ plasma to modify the surface of PP membranes
85 however they did not meet the standards of superhydrophobicity and contact angles only reached
86 105°. Thus, up to now plasma processing has been mostly employed for surface functionalization
87 and not for simultaneous surface and topography modification.

88

89 **Figure 1:** Schematic of flat sheet membranes before and after plasma treatment along with the
 90 corresponding cross-section SEM images and water contact angle photographs. The schematic in
 91 the middle shows the plasma treatment including: the O₂ etching step that creates roughness on
 92 the surface and the C₄F₈ deposition step that lowers the surface tension. Inside the circles we
 93 describe the MD working mechanism in each case by showing the liquid-air interface that takes
 94 place on the feed side and inside the pores.

95

96 Herein, we attempt for the first time to render both hydrophobic and hydrophilic commercial
 97 membranes superhydrophobic, using a two-step plasma treatment, which is a dry, green, and
 98 environmentally friendly approach, not requiring any wet or toxic chemistry (figure 1). In the
 99 first step, we modify the topography by creating micro and nanostructures on the membranes
 100 (micro-nanotexturing) using O₂ plasma reactive ion etching, a process which removes (etches)
 101 material from the top membrane surface [21], [22], [50]. Subsequently, by just switching the gas
 102 to octafluorocyclobutane (C₄F₈) (or other fluorocarbon or hydrocarbon) we alter the surface
 103 chemistry [51] by a thin hydrophobic layer deposition. This results in superhydrophobic
 104 membranes featuring contact angles above 150 ° and hysteresis below 10 ° even for liquids of 55

105 mN/m surface tension, with increased mean pore size, so that mass transfer is increased, while
106 maintaining high water Liquid Entry Pressure (LEP) values. LEP is the minimum pressure that
107 permits a liquid to penetrate the pores of a membrane in contact with the liquid. Plasma treated
108 membranes also feature increased porosity and decreased tortuosity, a value that as increases
109 beyond the ideal value of 1 so does the pore structure deviation from the straight, cylindrical
110 shape. Thus, the superhydrophobic plasma treated PTFE membranes not only did they not
111 exhibit reduced permeate flux as in previous reports, but showed an enhanced performance in
112 AGMD, presenting an increased flux compared to the pristine samples. At the same time, they
113 maintained a stable performance throughout the 48-h operations with extremely high salt
114 rejection rates (>99.99 %) and robust anti-wetting performance when SDS was added in the
115 saline solution. Even more significantly, Cellulose Acetate (CA) membranes, which were
116 unsuitable for MD due to their hydrophilic nature, have become capable of desalination,
117 exhibiting a stable performance with a salt rejection rate of 99.23 %.

118 **2. Experimental**

119 **2.1 Membrane materials**

120 Hydrophobic, polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) flat sheet membranes having mean pore sizes of
121 0.1, 0.2 and 1 μm and an average thickness of 150 μm (from now on referred to as PTFE 0.1,
122 PTFE 0.2, and PTFE 1) were kindly provided by Donaldson. The top layer is 30 μm thick
123 featuring a web-like mesh consisting of 50 nm thick PTFE fibers and to enhance mechanical
124 stability they also have a 120 μm polypropylene (PP) substrate featuring thicker fibers of 30 μm
125 in diameter. Hydrophilic, cellulose acetate (CA) membrane disks of 142 mm diameter with a
126 mean pore size of 0.22 μm and an average thickness of 90 μm (from now on referred to as CA
127 0.2) were supplied by Dorsan. They are sandwich-like structured where the top and bottom

128 layers are 30 μm thick each, consisting of a mesh of thin fibers, while the inner layer that
129 provides mechanical stability features thicker fibers.

130 **2.2 Plasma treatment of membranes**

131 All membranes were textured inside an Alcatel Reactive Ion Etcher (RIE) NE330 using 400 W
132 plasma power, 10 mTorr pressure and 100 sccm flow rate of O_2 . These conditions induce
133 directional (anisotropic) etching and result in roughness creation perpendicular to the surface of
134 the membrane. To further explain the roughness mechanism, we mention that small amounts of
135 etching inhibitors sputtered from the quartz plate (covering the electrode) deposit on the surface
136 of the polymer during O_2 plasma etching (the surface concentration in inhibitors is less than 4
137 %). They act as local micromasks during anisotropic polymer etching and result in nanogras
138 formation, which grows versus time in nanofilaments, and eventually bundled nanofilaments
139 [50],[52]. The same process has been used for roughness creation in various polymeric materials
140 in other plasma reactors, and it is extremely reproducible [20], [22], [52]–[54]. To avoid
141 membrane heating due to ion bombardment, 5-minute breaks were used after every 1.5 min of
142 plasma micro-nanotexturing. PTFE 0.1 and PTFE 0.2 were treated for 3 min on their top side.
143 PTFE 1 samples were textured for 1 minute due to the initially larger pore sizes since plasma
144 etching inherently widens the pores. CA 0.2 membranes were textured for 1 minute in each side.

145 The maximum allowable membrane plasma etching time was dictated by the need to preserve
146 enough top membrane layer, i.e., stop the etching well before reaching the membrane support.
147 For homogenous and non-porous film etching the maximum etching time is determined by the
148 film etching rate ER as:

$$149 \quad \text{time} = \frac{t_{final} - t_0}{ER} \quad (1),$$

150 Here, t_{final} is the desired final remaining thickness and t_0 the initial thickness. Thus, for 25 μm
151 film and typical etching rates of organic (e.g. acrylate) films being 0.5 $\mu\text{m}/\text{min}$ [18],[22], the
152 time to remove all the film would be approximately 50 min. However, as membranes are porous
153 with porosities ranged from 71 % to 81 % the apparent etching rate was much higher.
154 Determining an accurate etching rate was challenging, as it depends on porosity and tortuosity,
155 and can be done only indirectly. Indeed, for PTFE 0.1 and 0.2 membranes etched for 6 and 7 min
156 the LEP dropped to 0.1 bar, which indicates that the top layer was almost completely removed.
157 Therefore, for a 25 μm top layer thickness, this gives an etching rate larger than 3-4 $\mu\text{m}/\text{min}$. On
158 the other hand, the surface morphology (figure 3) as well as the LEP values (Table 2) indicate
159 that 4 min of etching did not destroy the top layer, on any of the PTFE membranes used. This
160 suggests that the etching rate was less than 6 $\mu\text{m}/\text{min}$. Similar observations for CA membranes
161 give a maximum etching time of 4 min since at this time the membrane support was exposed,
162 while at typical etching time of 2 min no membrane support was detected in SEM images. Given
163 that the top layer thickness of CA membranes was 30 μm , the etching rate is between 6 and 7
164 $\mu\text{m}/\text{min}$. Assuming typical etching times of 2 min, and etching rates on the order of 5 $\mu\text{m}/\text{min}$,
165 we get a total top layer thickness loss of 10 μm , i.e., about 11 % of the total membrane thickness
166 for the PTFE, 6 % for the CA membranes and about 35 % of the top 25 μm layer thickness.

167 After the O_2 plasma texturing, membranes were transferred inside a high-density Inductively
168 Coupled Plasma (ICP) reactor equipped with a helicon source (at 13.56 MHz), the MET system
169 of Adixen for the deposition process. This step incorporates Octafluorocyclobutane (C_4F_8)
170 plasma to deposit a thin hydrophobic film of 30 nm (as measured on flat Silicon wafer), reduce
171 the surface energy, and render the surface of the membranes superhydrophobic. The conditions
172 used were the following: plasma power 900 W, pressure 5.33 Pa, C_4F_8 flow rate 25 sccm, 0 W

173 bias, electrode temperature 0 °C, and 1 minute 20 seconds duration on both sides for all the
174 PTFE and 4 minutes on both sides for the CA membranes. From now on, we will refer to the
175 textured and hydrophobized membranes as plasma treated membranes. It should be stressed here
176 that other less fluorinated or non-fluorinated gases may be used for membrane hydrophobization,
177 such as CHF₃, or hydrocarbons. However, C₄F₈ plasma deposited films have lower surface
178 energy.

179 **2.3 Membrane characterization**

180 Morphological characterization of the produced membranes was performed using a JEOL JSM-
181 7401F FEG, scanning electron microscope, at 2 kV beam voltage after coating with a conductive
182 platinum coating of typical thickness of 2 nm on a flat substrate. For the water static contact
183 angle (WSCA) and contact angle hysteresis (CAH) characterization a Kruess DSA 100 system
184 was used.

185 WSCA were measured using DI water droplets of 5 µl and 1.6 % w/w, 4 % w/w, 8 % w/w and
186 16.5 % w/w isopropanol-in-water mixtures with surface tensions of 65, 55, 44, and 31 mN/m at
187 20 °C (D.I. water has surface tension 72 mN/m), respectively. CAH was measured by increasing
188 and decreasing the drop volume from 3 µl to 20 µl following the needle method. The advancing
189 contact angle was measured as the contact line between the substrate and the drop increases,
190 while the receding contact angle was measured as the contact line withdraws. The difference
191 between advancing and receding contact angle was the CAH. The WCA and CAH measurements
192 were repeated at least 3 times for each membrane.

193 Liquid Entry Pressure (LEP) is the minimum pressure that permits a liquid to penetrate the pores
194 of a membrane in contact with the liquid [55]. To measure the LEP, membranes were cut in

195 circular disks of 4 cm diameter and fixed in a special pressure module with a water inlet and
196 outlet on the topside and a backside made of perforated transparent polymethyl methacrylate.
197 Each time the membrane was penetrated by water, droplets formed and were observed on the
198 backside. The pressure of the liquid was regulated via a gear pump connected to a digital
199 pressure meter with a resolution of 0.01 bar. In a measurement the pressure was increased in
200 steps of 0.1 bar and intervals of at least 10–15 min before switching to the next pressure. Upon
201 successive increments the LEP was defined as the pressure at which a single droplet was
202 observed on the backside of the module. Using the Young-Laplace equation [56] one can
203 estimate the maximum pore radius r_{max} for each LEP value:

$$204 \quad r_{max} = \frac{-2\gamma_l \cos \theta}{LEP} \quad (2)$$

205 where γ_l is liquid surface tension (in this case water) and with the assumption that pores have
206 cylindrical shapes.

207 To measure porosity membrane pieces of mass greater than 1 g were cut and weighted.
208 Afterwards they were completely soaked in isopropanol to allow complete imbibition into the
209 pores. Then absorbing papers were placed on either side of the samples to wipe the excess liquid
210 followed by weight measurement. This procedure was repeated at least five times until constant
211 values were reached. Porosity ε was calculated as:

$$212 \quad \varepsilon = \frac{(w_{iso+pol} - w_{pol})/\rho_{iso}}{(w_{iso+pol} - w_{pol})/\rho_{iso} + w_{pol}/\rho_{pol}} \quad (3)$$

213 where, w_{pol} is the weight of the membrane sample, $w_{iso+pol}$ is the weight of the membrane
214 sample soaked in isopropanol, ρ_{iso} is the density of isopropanol and ρ_{pol} is the density of the
215 polymer of the membrane material [55].

216 Tortuosity can be calculated when porosity is known using the following equation, proposed by
217 Mackie and Meares [57] which is considered the most accurate [58]:

$$218 \quad \tau = \frac{(2 - \varepsilon)^2}{\varepsilon} \quad (4)$$

219 **2.4 Air Gap Membrane Distillation Setup**

220

221 A lab-scale setup for Air Gap Membrane Distillation (AGMD) was established to test the
222 performance of membranes (figure 2). The tested membrane was mounted in a module
223 contacting the saline water in a feed flow channel on the frontside. The condensing surface was
224 placed on the backside after an air gap width of ~3.5 mm. A thermostat water circulation bath
225 heated the feed saline water to the required temperature. A conductivity meter measured the
226 salinity, and a magnetic coupling water pump was used to reach the flow rate needed for the
227 experiment. The hot saline water returned to the feed container after it passed over the membrane
228 surface. Due to the pressure gradient across the membrane, caused by the temperature difference
229 on each side, water vapor passed through the membrane pores and condensed on the surface of a
230 cold condensation plate (copper heat sink) on the permeate side that was in contact with a cold-
231 water flow. The temperature of the coolant circulation was controlled by a refrigerated water
232 bath circulator (F25-HE, Julabo). Permeate water was collected in a water tank where its
233 conductivity and weight (SPX 2202, Ohaus) were continuously measured.

234 Distillation flux was calculated by the following equation [59]:

235
$$J = \frac{\text{Increase in permeate weight}}{\text{Area} * \text{time}} \quad (5)$$

236 The conductivity of feed water was always maintained at 54 mS/cm and using the conductivity
 237 of permeate water produced, the salt rejection was calculated by the formula:

238
$$\text{Salt rejection} = \left(1 - \frac{\text{Conductivity of permeate water}}{\text{Conductivity of feed water}} \right) * 100 \% \quad (6)$$

239 Hence distillation flux and the conductivity were continuously measured by a conductivity
 240 meter, temperature probes (PM-1/10-1/8-6-0-P-3, Omega), pressure transducers (IPSLU-M12,
 241 RS-Pro) and flow meters (FT110, Gems) that were installed in the setup. We continuously
 242 monitored salt rejection, flow rate and pressure in the feed and in the coolant loop. A data
 243 acquisition system, consisting of two National Instruments (NI) analog input modules (PCI 6251
 244 and NI-9216) was connected to all the sensors. Therefore, all measured data was monitored in
 245 real-time and stored in a computer utilizing a home written LabView code. All commercial and
 246 plasma-treated membranes were tested using this AGMD setup. This setup could provide a
 247 continuous test for more than 40 hours with stabilized feed water temperature, pressure, flow rate
 248 and salinity. MD operating conditions are presented on Table 1. For the anti-wetting evaluation
 249 0.01 mM of sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) was added to the saline solution corresponding to
 250 surface tension of 55 mN/m. The operating conditions are the same as for standard MD.

251

252 **Table 1** Operating parameters for AGMD tests

Variables	Values

Feed inlet temperature	75 °C for PTFE membranes 65 °C for CA membranes
Feed flow rate	1 L/min
Reynolds number	~1870
Feed pressure	~0.2 bar
Coolant temperature	15 °C for PTFE membranes 10 °C for CA membranes
Coolant flow rate	2 L/min
Air gap width	3.5 mm
Effective membrane area	38 cm ²
Concentration of NaCl	0.59 M
Concentration of SDS	0.01 mM
Feed conductivity @ 22 °C	54 mS/cm
Test duration	48 h

254

255 **Figure 2:** Schematic of the air gap membrane distillation (AGMD) setup.

256

257 **3. Results and discussion**

258 **3.1 Membrane Characterization**

259 SEM images (figure 3) reveal topographical changes caused by etching for the surfaces of PTFE
 260 and CA membranes. The characteristic top-surface fibers disappeared and the mean distance
 261 between the structures that are formed increased with etching time. On the 2 min O₂ plasma the
 262 pores are widened and at the 4 min duration this effect is maximized. Plasma treatment led to
 263 pronounced peaks and valleys on the nano and microscale. This particular rough topography
 264 (which we term micro-nanotexturing) leads to a high surface air fraction, which is crucial to
 265 achieve superhydrophobicity [54],[60]. The height of structures and their spacing increased as a
 266 function of processing time in the O₂ plasma. Therefore, the mean pore size follows the same
 267 trend.

268 This trend could be quantified through a more systematic analysis of the SEM images based on
269 the assumption that the membrane pores can be identified by the darkest areas of images. This
270 approach for membrane pore quantification is briefly explained below, while it will be a subject
271 of a future publication: the key point enabling the identification of the darkest regions in images
272 is that the histogram of pixel intensities of most images exhibits a local minimum at some low
273 pixel intensity. This intensity can be used as threshold to separate the dark pore areas from the
274 brighter ones coming from the membrane material of fibers. Since the pore areas have been
275 defined on the analyzed SEM image, we can report their positions and sizes and make their
276 statistical analysis to quantify the changes induced by plasma treatment (more details about the
277 methodology followed can be found in the supporting information file). The analysis shows that
278 plasma etching increased the mean and the maximum pore diameter in all membranes (figure 3 J,
279 K).

Figure 3. SEM images showing the top view of PTFE 0.1 μm membranes in (A) pristine condition, (B) after 2 min and (C) 4 min of O₂ plasma nanotexturing respectively. (D), (E) and (F) are the same nanotexturing duration for the case of the PTFE 0.2 μm membranes while (G), (H) and (I) are the same nanotexturing duration for the CA 0.22 μm membranes. In all cases the mean distance between the structures, and thus the pore size, increased proportionally to the etching duration. The effect is more apparent in the CA 0.22 μm membranes since this material shows a higher etching rate. All PTFE membranes were coated for 1 min and 20 s on both sides

and the CA membranes were coated for 4 min on both sides using C₄F₈ plasma deposition. (J) Mean pore size and (K) maximum pore size for PTFE 0.1, 0.2 and CA 0.22 membranes versus O₂ plasma nanotexturing duration as obtained by top-down SEM image analysis.

280

281 CA membranes were more sensitive to O₂ plasma etching, in the sense that they exhibit faster
282 etching rates. After 4 min the top layer was completely etched away and some fibers from the
283 membrane support material started to appear. Therefore, 1 min O₂ plasma on both sides was
284 considered the safest option for the CA membranes since micro-nano textures created provided
285 the necessary roughness for superhydrophobicity. For the PTFE 0.1 and 0.2 membranes we
286 proceeded with 3 min of O₂ etching on the top side, while the PTFE 1 μm was etched for 1 min
287 on the top side. As explained in the experimental section, the deposition duration of C₄F₈ for all
288 PTFE samples was 1 min and 20 s on both sides and on the CA samples it was 4 min on both
289 sides.

290 We measured the WSCA and CAH of membranes using DI water (figure 4). All plasma treated
291 membranes were superhydrophobic, at least on the topside that is in contact with the feed saline
292 water. WSCAs were above 150 ° and CAHs below 10 °, while pristine membranes were simply
293 hydrophobic in the case of PTFE and hydrophilic in the case of CA (therefore we do not show
294 untreated CA in figure 4). The WSCA remained above 150 ° in all plasma treated membranes
295 when using liquids of lower surface tension and only started to slightly decrease, reaching 140 °,
296 when the surface tension dropped below 45 mN/m. At the same time, CAH started to rise beyond
297 10 ° but not above 20 ° when the surface tension of the liquid dropped below 55 mN/m, showing
298 that the membranes become sticky, and the super liquid repellency was lost between 55 and
299 45mN/m. In the case of untreated PTFE membranes, the WSCA remained below 140 ° for all

300 liquids above 45 mN/m and dropped even more when the surface tension decreased beyond that
 301 value. The above results further indicate the capability of plasma treated membranes to be used
 302 in desalination of sea water where the surfactants, oils and bio-foulants would reduce the surface
 303 tension.

Figure 4: Water contact angle and hysteresis of the top side of plasma nanotextured PTFE and CA membranes as a function of surface tension (dashed lines added to guide the eye). The liquids used were water ($\gamma = 72$ mN/m), isopropanol/water 1.6 % w/w ($\gamma = 65$ mN/m), isopropanol/water 4 % w/w ($\gamma = 55$ mN/m,) isopropanol/water 8 % w/w ($\gamma = 44$ mN/m), and isopropanol/water 16.5 % w/w ($\gamma = 31$ mN/m). The lines at 150° (contact angle) and at 10° (hysteresis) mark the limits for superhydrophobicity.

304

305 The porosities of all plasma treated membranes were not increased more than 8 % (Table 2). We
 306 explain this observation with the hierarchical structure of membranes. The inner layers are not

307 affected by the bombardment of ions, and we can safely presume that they maintain their
308 structural integrity.

309 As tortuosity increases beyond the ideal value of 1, which corresponds to a membrane featuring
310 perfectly cylindrical pores, the mass transfer resistance also increases, while permeate flux
311 decreases [3]. This can be easily explained when the inner structures of the pores deviate from a
312 simple cylindrical shape, water vapor transport becomes harder as it must travel a greater
313 distance. In our case tortuosity decreases after the plasma treatment, which is a consequence of
314 the increase in porosity, and hence the permeate flux is expected to also increase.

315 LEP is a crucial property which describes whether a membrane can withstand the hydrostatic
316 pressure and avoid wetting. The LEPs of all membranes were above the critical point of 1 bar
317 (Table 2). Results further indicate that plasma treatment widens the pores since all plasma treated
318 membranes had lower LEPs compared to pristine samples. As expected, the untreated PTFE 0.1
319 had the highest value, due to its smallest mean pore size, at 7.9 bar. After 3 min of plasma
320 etching and fluorination, the LEP had decreased to 6.6 bar. This $\approx 20\%$ reduction in LEP is
321 noticed in all plasma treated PTFE samples compared to the untreated ones.

322 Plasma-induced pore widening is more apparent in the case of PTFE 1 where for the untreated it
323 was calculated 550 to 600 nm and for the plasma treated it was found twice as large, proving that
324 O_2 etching has a dramatic effect in porous materials featuring large pores initially. We stress here
325 that the CA membrane which is hydrophilic and shows complete wetting when exposed to water,
326 after the fluorination step during the plasma treatment shows 1.8 bar LEP, which makes it usable
327 for MD. This again shows the potential of our proposed technology.

328 **Table 2**

329 Experimentally measured and calculated properties of the membranes used in this work.

Membrane Type	Porosity (%)	LEP (bar)	Maximum pore diameter from LEP (nm)	Tortuosity
PTFE 0.1	56 ± 4	7.9 ± 0.4	260 ± 14	3.7
PTFE 0.1 plasma treated	63 ± 3	6.6 ± 0.3	410 ± 18	2.9
PTFE 0.2	59 ± 3	5.5 ± 0.5	372 ± 34	3.4
PTFE 0.2 plasma treated	62 ± 4	4.8 ± 0.2	576 ± 24	3.1
PTFE 1	61 ± 4	1.9 ± 0.1	1172 ± 62	3.2
PTFE 1 plasma treated	67 ± 5	1.3 ± 0.1	2162 ± 166	2.6
CA 0.22	77 ± 4			2.0
CA 0.22 plasma treated	81 ± 3	1.8 ± 0.2	1574 ± 174	1.7

330

331 3.2 Air Gap Membrane Distillation performance

332

333 Plasma treated membranes exhibit lower tortuosity (improved pore shape) and increased porosity
334 values compared to untreated ones (Table 2). Mass transfer coefficient is proportional to porosity
335 [61] and the fact that O₂ plasma etching increases porosity suggests that it plays a dominant role
336 in the permeate flux increase of all plasma treated membranes.

337 Due to its largest pore size, the plasma treated PTFE 1 membrane yields, as expected, the highest
338 flux at 10.9 L/m²h when compared to the other plasma treated PTFE membranes (figure 5C).

339 However, in addition to wetting control, plasma treatment enables the permeate water fluxes of

340 the plasma treated PTFE 0.1 and PTFE 0.2 membranes to exceed that of the untreated PTFE 1
341 membrane. We have found that plasma treatment enhances the performance of commercial
342 PTFE membranes by 10-15 % in average, as shown in the diagrams of permeate flux and salt
343 rejection versus time (figure 5A, B and C). This increased flux is attributed to
344 superhydrophobicity, increased pore size, porosity as well as decreased tortuosity. The AGMD
345 result of the plasma treated CA 0.22 membrane is shown in figure 5 D. The MD temperatures of
346 these experiments are slightly lower (feed: 65 °C, coolant: 10 °C), since CA is more sensitive to
347 temperature than PTFE, but the temperature difference is in the same range (55-60 °C).
348 However, the flux is once again increased by almost 15 % compared to the flux of the untreated
349 PTFE 0.2 membrane tested at the same temperatures ($6.05 \text{ Lm}^{-2}\text{h}^{-1}$).

350 The performance of all plasma treated membranes remained stable throughout the whole
351 duration (48 hours) of the experiments. In contrast, all untreated PTFE membranes exhibited a
352 lower distillation flux. For PTFE 1 and PTFE 0.2 the fluxes also decreased over time, possibly
353 due to their vulnerability to scaling or partial wetting of the pore mouths. Specifically, the
354 distillation flux of untreated PTFE 1 membrane constantly decreased from 10.7 to 9.9 $\text{L/m}^2\text{h}$,
355 whereas on the plasma treated PTFE 1 membrane, the performance was constant at 10.9 - 11
356 $\text{L/m}^2\text{h}$. Similarly, in the case of untreated PTFE 0.2, the flux decreased from 10.3 to 9.7 $\text{L/m}^2\text{h}$,
357 while on the plasma treated PTFE 0.2 membrane remained constant at 10.8 - 10.9 $\text{L/m}^2\text{h}$.
358 Moreover, the performance of the plasma treated CA 0.22 also remained stable throughout the
359 experiment. This suggests that the structures created via plasma treatment are durable, while the
360 treatment provides an increased flux compared to the corresponding, in terms of mean pore size,
361 hydrophobic PTFE membrane. These observations prove that plasma treatment induced

362 superhydrophobicity increases the flux by widening the pores while also provides stable and
 363 durable structures, able to resist wetting in long term operation.

364 The long-term experiments also indicate that the hydrophobization step reached the inner parts of
 365 the pores; no capillary condensation and membrane wetting during MD was observed.
 366 Furthermore, the stable performance of all plasma treated membranes can be interpreted as
 367 evidence of scaling resistance deriving from the superhydrophobic properties, since soluble salts
 368 are prone to deposit on the surface of non-superhydrophobic membranes, clogging the pores and
 369 decreasing the flux of distilled water, as we see in the case of untreated PTFE 0.2 and PTFE 1
 370 membranes.

371

372 **Figure 5:** AGMD performance in terms of distillation flux and salt rejection versus time of
373 PTFE 0.1 (A), PTFE 0.2 (B) and PTFE 1 (C) plasma treated and untreated, and plasma treated
374 CA 0.22 (D) membranes. See Table 1 for operating conditions.

375

376 The Salt Rejection rate values were calculated by inserting the final conductivity values at the
377 end of a 48-h operation using the equation (6) described in paragraph 2.4. All PTFE membranes,
378 plasma treated and pristine, exhibited an excellent salt rejection rate, higher than 99.99 %, which
379 corresponds to permeate water with conductivity in the range of distilled water. In the case of
380 plasma treated CA membranes the salt rejection rate is 99.23 %.

381 Since plasma treated membranes remain superhydrophobic down to 55 mN/M, as determined by
382 the WSCA shown in figure 4, their anti-wetting properties were evaluated by using a solution of
383 the same surface tension. SDS of 0.01 mM was added to the saline solution of the standard MD
384 tests and the anti-wetting performance of PTFE 0.2 plasma treated membranes was evaluated
385 (figure 6). The high LEP value along with the excellent WSCA and hysteresis values of this
386 membrane were the encouraging factors on which we based the choice to use it. Permeate flux
387 was measured at 9.5-9.6 Lm⁻²h⁻¹ and salt rejection was 99.99 % at the end of the experiment.
388 This result indicates that plasma treatment is capable to produce durable and robust membranes
389 when used against low surface tension liquids. The reduced flux compared to standard MD is
390 attributed to the reduced liquid-air interface, due to the reduced surface tension, causing
391 increased mass transfer resistance. For comparison purposes we stress that PTFE 0.2 untreated
392 was not able to maintain a stable performance even on standard MD since flux was constantly
393 decreasing; on the contrary for the plasma treated membranes flux was stable throughout the 48
394 hours. This promising result suggests that plasma treated membranes could be thoroughly tested

395 for their anti-wetting and anti-fouling properties in the future against conditions commonly found
396 in real seawater.

397

398 **Figure 6:** Anti-wetting performance of PTFE 0.2 in AGMD using 0.01 mM of SDS
399 corresponding to 55 mN/m surface tension.

400

401 4. Conclusions

402 In this work we have rendered commercial membranes superhydrophobic regardless of their
403 initial wetting properties by utilizing plasma etching followed by plasma deposition; a new, dry
404 and environmentally friendly method. Roughness on the surface was achieved by micro and
405 nanotexturing with O₂ plasma while surface energy was lowered with the use of C₄F₈ plasma
406 deposition. The plasma treated membranes had contact angles above 150 ° and a hysteresis
407 below 10 ° even for liquids of 55 mN/m surface tension. The LEP values were not substantially
408 reduced although pore widening was observed after the plasma treatment while AGMD flux and
409 salt rejection rate of plasma treated PTFE membranes was improved. Their performance was

410 stable for at least 48 h using standard saline water and remained stable with excellent salt
411 rejection when SDS was added in the feed solution, suggesting the potential of our technique for
412 the fabrication of membranes with anti-wetting properties. Additionally, we have managed to
413 render an initially hydrophilic CA membrane capable for MD that also exhibited a stable
414 performance with a sufficient salt rejection rate, further proving that plasma technology is a new,
415 green, and powerful tool in the enhancement of membranes' performance.

416 **Nomenclature**

417 *Symbols*

418 B = gas permeance [$\text{mol}/(\text{m}^2 \text{ s Pa})$]

419 C = conductivity ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$)

420 ER = etching rate ($\mu\text{m}/\text{min}$)

421 F = Flux [$\text{L}/(\text{m}^2\text{min})$]

422 L effective pore length (m)

423 LEP = Liquid Entry Pressure (Pa)

424 M = molecular weight (g/mol)

425 P = pressure (Pa)

426 R = gas constant [$\text{m}^3 \text{ Pa}/(\text{K mol})$]

427 r = pore radius (m)

428 SR = salt rejection

429 T = temperature (K)

430 t = thickness (μm)

431 $time$ = time (min)

432 w = weight (g)

433 *Greek Letters*

434 γ = surface tension (N/m)

435 ε = porosity

436 μ = viscosity [kg/(m s)]

437 ρ = density (g/m³)

438 τ = tortuosity

439 *Subscripts*

440 *F* = feed saline water

441 *final* = final value

442 *iso* = isopropanol

443 *l* = liquid

444 *m* = membrane

445 *max* = maximum

446 *o* = initial value

447 *P* = permeate water

448 *p* = pore

449 *pol* = membrane polymer

450

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454

455 **5. References**

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